

Mapping the evidence behind mineral content in fortification products for preterm infants – a scoping review

Authors

Marie Bendix Simonsen^{1, 2}, Karina Dyrvig Honoré^{1, 2}, Per Torp Sangild^{2, 3, 4} Gitte Zachariassen^{1, 2}

¹Hans Christian Andersen Children's Hospital, Odense University Hospital, Odense; ²Department of Clinical Research, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, ³Section of Comparative Paediatrics and Nutrition, University of Copenhagen, Frederiksberg; ⁴Department of Neonatology, Copenhagen University Hospital Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen

Abbreviations and definitions:

VPI = Very preterm infants born before 32 weeks of gestation

MOM = Mother's own milk

DHM = Donor human milk

Micronutrients = vitamins and minerals needed by the body in small amounts and deficiency can cause life threatening conditions

RCT: Randomized controlled trial

Introduction

Very preterm infants (VPI) have high nutritional demands after birth in order to achieve proper growth and development. In addition, they are born with low body stores of a multitude of micronutrients, vitamins, and minerals, since the accretion of these primarily takes place during the third trimester (1, 2). Optimal nutritional management of these infants is further complicated by their very immature organ systems, especially the gut and acute onset of severe illness, which puts them at high risk of deficiencies and malnutrition. In order to meet these high demands, it requires specialized products with high nutritional quality.

The preferred nutrition for all preterm infants is human milk, either mother's own milk (MOM) or donor human milk (DHM). However, the nutritional adequacy of MOM differs between feedings and among mothers (3-5). DHM is milk from the state of lactation where protein content is lowest, and furthermore, some of the nutrients and bioactive components of donor human milk are lost during processing (6). Consequently, neither MOM – nor DHM contain sufficient levels of nutrients to support the high demands of the very preterm infant. Therefore, fortification of human milk with both macro- and micronutrients has become standard practice, in order to avoid deficiencies that could lead to short-term growth failure, impaired neurodevelopment, and deficiency disorders later in life. Despite great improvements in fortification products for preterm infants during the last decade, micronutrient deficits remain a present problem among infants born preterm (7). A lot of focus has been on the ideal protein content in these fortification products. On the contrary evidence from randomized controlled trials (RCT) or other trials, concerning the content of minerals and their clinical relevance is low (8, 9). In contrast to medications developed and produced by the pharmaceutical industry, companies who produce fortification products are not imputed to the same level of control from the authorities, as fortification products are categorized as "dietary supplements and infant formula". The manufacturers of fortification products need to base the content of their products on international recommendations from scientific societies like the European Society of Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition (ESPGHAN), and it is recommended that the product is tested with relevant scientific studies, but this is not mandatory. Therefore, it is up to the company to assess the need for clinical studies and further to ensure the content of the product, since the authorities do not perform routine control.

Recent studies have reported that regardless of fortification, both DM and MOM fail to meet the recommended nutrient intake for both energy (10), protein (11), and micronutrients (12). When examining the nutritional composition of commercially available fortifiers, they are very heterogeneous in micronutrient content, see Table 1.

Table 1:

Examples of varying micronutrient content in selected commercially available fortification products pr. 100mL fortified milk

Name	Pre-NAN FM85	Enfamil	Similac	Nutricia Human Milk Fortifier	HMBF+4
Manufacturer	Nestlé	Mead-Johnson/Reckitt	Abbott	Danone/Nutricia	Prolacta
Calcium (mg)	76	53	116	95	114.8
Phosphorus (mg)	44	29	64	52	64.7
Iron (mg)	1.8	1.2	0.32	0	0.1

However, the rationale behind these variations is not known. Recently ESPGHAN published a position paper concerning enteral nutrition for preterm infants (13). Compared to the 2010 position paper (14) the recommended intake for several micronutrients, including calcium and phosphate, have been increased. These recommendations are based on in-utero accretion rates at different stages of gestation, and recommend how much preterm infants at different weights and gestational ages should receive on a daily basis. To our knowledge, no reviews cover the evidence for the micronutrient content in fortification products and if these have ever been investigated in a clinical setting. A preliminary search of MEDLINE, the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, and *JBI Evidence Synthesis* was conducted in May 2023, and no current or underway systematic or scoping reviews on this topic were identified.

With this scoping review, we aim to map the current state of evidence for the micronutrient content in fortification products for preterm infants and secondly, to identify eventual gaps in the literature.

Research questions

1. What types of evidence (clinical studies, retrospective studies, theoretical calculations, clinical study reports from the industry, etc.) exist for the micronutrient content in fortification products for very preterm infants?
2. Is there gaps in the literature? If so, we aim to describe those gaps and their clinical relevance, in order to set up areas for new studies.

Keywords

Nutrition; preterm infants; human milk fortification; micronutrients, vitamins, minerals

Methods

This scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews and reported using the PRISMA guidelines for scoping reviews.

Eligibility criteria

Participants

The recommendations and literature should comprise fortification of human milk (MOM and DHM) for very preterm infants (born at or before 32 weeks or below 1800 grams at birth), who are hospitalized and receiving fortification.

Concept

All kinds of literature reporting micronutrient content in fortification products for very preterm infants will be reviewed.

Context

We will include all types of quantitative studies published within the last 10 years, including animal studies, calculations, industrial studies, and models. The study must be published in English, Danish, Norwegian, or Swedish and be available in full-text version. Studies from low-income countries will not be included since the population, treatment opportunities and NICU setting are very different from the population we aim to investigate.

Inclusion criteria

- Studies evaluating on a single micronutrient in a fortification product
- Studies evaluating several micronutrients in a fortification product
- Studies evaluating the both macro- and micronutrients in a fortification product

Exclusion criteria

- Studies on post-hospital discharge fortification
- Studies evaluating micronutrients given as supplements to fortification
- Preterm infants suffering from conditions requiring abdominal surgery
- Retracted article
- Full text not available
- Duplicate or overlapping study population

Types of sources

This scoping review will consider both experimental and quasi-experimental study designs including randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, observational studies, and cross-sectional studies. In addition, industrial papers will be considered for inclusion. Furthermore, systematic reviews that meet the inclusion criteria will also be considered, depending on the research question. Likewise, text, theoretical calculations and opinion papers.

Step 2: Identifying relevant studies

Search strategy

The search strategy will aim to locate both published and unpublished studies. An initial limited search of MEDLINE was undertaken to identify articles on the topic. The initial search strategy used the following keywords: Preterm infants, premature infants, VLBW infants, very low birth weight infants, ELBW infants, extremely low birth weight infants, immature infants, Human milk fortifier, nutrition enrichment, fortification, multi-nutrient fortifier, vitamins, minerals, nutriments, micronutrients, nutritional supplements and trace minerals. Hereafter a librarian is consulted to ensure that all key terms and concepts were covered.

The text words contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, and the index terms used to describe the articles were used to develop a full search strategy for Embase, Medline, Cochrane, and Scopus. Sources of unpublished studies are to be searched including references. We aim to contact the manufacturers of the fortification products for their documents, clinical study reports, and recommendations/guidelines (*relevant databases/information sources*) (see Appendix #) if available. The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be adapted for each included database and/or information source. The reference list of all included sources of evidence will be screened for additional studies.

Studies published in English or Danish will be included. Clinical published from 2010 until 2023 will be included as there have been major changes in the practice for the nutrition of preterm infants with European (ESPGHAN) and American nutrition guidelines for preterm infants published in 2010 and 2013, respectively and those have lately been revised.

Step 3: Selecting the studies

Following the search, all identified citations will be collected and uploaded into Covidence and duplicates removed. Two independent, blinded reviewers (MBS and KDH) will screen titles and abstracts by using the Participants – Concept- Context framework to identify if the articles meet the basic inclusion criteria. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full text. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail and held up against the inclusion criteria by the same two reviewers (MBS and KDH). Reasons for the exclusion of sources of evidence in the full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion. If agreement is not reached, an additional third reviewer (GZ) will be consulted.

The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram.

Step 4: Charting the data

Data will be blindly extracted from papers included in the scoping review by MBS and KDH, using a data extraction tool developed by the primary investigator (MBS). The data extracted will include specific details about the participants, concept, context, study methods and key findings relevant to the review questions and will include: Title, publication year, country, authors, journal, type of study, research objective, setting, population including sample size, data collection methods, fortification product, and outcomes measures.

A draft extraction form is provided in appendix (see Appendix XX). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the final scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer (PS or GZ).

Step 5: Collecting, summarising, and reporting results

We plan to summarize study types in a tabular format. Evidence and gaps from the selected studies will be summarized as an evidence gap map according to each micronutrient, product, or study type, depending on the literature.

Funding

This study is funded by the OUH Ph.d. grant and the University of Southern Denmark.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have no conflicts to declare

References

1. Sethi A, Priyadarshi M, Agarwal R. Mineral and bone physiology in the foetus, preterm and full-term neonates. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2020;25(1):101076.
2. Abrams SA. In utero physiology: role in nutrient delivery and fetal development for calcium, phosphorus, and vitamin D. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2007;85(2):604s-7s.
3. de Halleux V, Pieltain C, Senterre T, Studzinski F, Kessen C, Rigo V, et al. Growth Benefits of Own Mother's Milk in Preterm Infants Fed Daily Individualized Fortified Human Milk. *Nutrients.* 2019;11(4).
4. John A, Sun R, Maillart L, Schaefer A, Hamilton Spence E, Perrin MT. Macronutrient variability in human milk from donors to a milk bank: Implications for feeding preterm infants. *PLoS One.* 2019;14(1):e0210610.
5. Gates A, Marin T, De Leo G, Waller JL, Stansfield BK. Nutrient composition of preterm mother's milk and factors that influence nutrient content. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2021;114(5):1719-28.
6. Peila C, Moro GE, Bertino E, Cavallarin L, Giribaldi M, Giuliani F, et al. The Effect of Holder Pasteurization on Nutrients and Biologically-Active Components in Donor Human Milk: A Review. *Nutrients.* 2016;8(8).
7. Högberg U, Winbo J, Fellman V. Population-based register study of children born in Sweden from 1997 to 2014 showed an increase in rickets during infancy. *Acta Paediatr.* 2019;108(11):2034-40.
8. Edmond K, Strobel N. Evidence for Global Health Care Interventions for Preterm or Low Birth Weight Infants: An Overview of Systematic Reviews. *Pediatrics.* 2022;150(Suppl 1).
9. Harding JE, Wilson J, Brown J. Calcium and phosphorus supplementation of human milk for preterm infants. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2017;2(2):Cd003310.
10. Newkirk M, Shakeel F, Parimi P, Rothpletz-Puglia P, Patusco R, Marcus AF, et al. Comparison of Calorie and Protein Intake of Very Low Birth Weight Infants Receiving Mother's Own Milk or Donor Milk When the Nutrient Composition of Human Milk Is Measured With a Breast Milk Analyzer. *Nutr Clin Pract.* 2018;33(5):679-86.

11. Krcho P, Vojtova V, Benesova M. Analysis of Human Milk Composition After Preterm Delivery With and Without Fortification. *Matern Child Health J.* 2015;19(8):1657-61.
12. Koo W, Tice H. Human Milk Fortifiers Do Not Meet the Current Recommendation for Nutrients in Very Low Birth Weight Infants. *JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr.* 2018;42(4):813-20.
13. Embleton ND, Jennifer Moltu S, Lapillonne A, van den Akker CHP, Carnielli V, Fusch C, et al. Enteral Nutrition in Preterm Infants (2022): A Position Paper From the ESPGHAN Committee on Nutrition and Invited Experts. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2023;76(2):248-68.
14. Agostoni C, Buonocore G, Carnielli VP, De Curtis M, Darmaun D, Decsi T, et al. Enteral nutrient supply for preterm infants: commentary from the European Society of Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition Committee on Nutrition. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2010;50(1):85-91.

Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument